

The Effect of Organ of Corti Fluid Tunnels on Cochlear Traveling Waves

Yanli Wang^{1,2} and Sunil Puria^{1,2,3,a)}

¹*Dept. of Otolaryngology, Harvard Medical School, Boston, MA.*

²*Eaton-Peabody Laboratories, Massachusetts Eye & Ear, Boston, MA.*

³*Graduate Program in Speech and Hearing Bioscience and Technology, Harvard University, Cambridge, MA.*

a) Corresponding author: sunil_puria@meei.harvard.edu

Abstract. Tapered “box models” are commonly used to study traveling wave in the cochlea. Many box models ignore the effect of the organ of Corti (OoC) on the traveling wave within the cochlea. Current work studies the potential effect of the OoC on the basilar membrane (BM) traveling wave through finite element modeling of various simplified OoC formulations within the box model. The results indicate that an added OoC with fluid tunnel(s) effectively decreases the phase roll-off found in box models that otherwise do not have an OoC.

INTRODUCTION

For both analytical and computational approaches, the tapered ‘box model’ is frequently used to study traveling wave mechanics in the cochlea. In these box models, a radially orthotropic basilar membrane (BM) without the organ of Corti (OoC) is fairly common. This is especially true for analytical models including asymptotic methods^{1,2}. However, the potential effect of the OoC and the fluid tunnels has not been systematically studied. In current work, results of BM-only box model and different simplifications for the OoC and fluid tunnel spaces were studied and compared systematically using the Finite Element Method (FEM) approach for the mouse cochlea.

METHODS

The baseline representation of the simplified OoC had a cross-section of a semi-circle and an off-centered fluid tunnel in the longitudinal direction through the length of the cochlea (Fig. 1a). Three different variations of the baseline representation of OoC were studied: Fig. 1b with a larger fluid tunnel; Fig. 1c with no fluid tunnel; Fig. 1d with two fluid tunnels. In addition, a BM only model without OoC was also studied. The BM was modeled as transversely orthotropic, while for simplicity the OoC was isotropic and elastic with damping. The material properties of the BM and OoC of the baseline model were tuned by matching the frequency-place map. The material properties were then kept same for all the variations.

FIGURE 1. (a-d) Cross-sectional view of the simplified organ of Corti (OoC) for the baseline model and its three variations. (a) baseline with one tunnel. (b) with a larger tunnel. (c) with no tunnel. (d) with two tunnels.

TABLE 1. Geometry and material properties of the full-length model^{3,4}. Linear interpolation was used between longitudinal locations.

Longitudinal location ($L_{BM} = 5.8$ mm)	0	$L_{BM}/3$	$L_{BM}^*/3/5$	L_{BM}
BM width	64 μm	-	-	118 μm
BM thickness	14 μm	-	-	4.8 μm
E_{BM} , radial	18 MPa	3.5 MPa	3.2 MPa	1 MPa
E_{BM} , long. and trans.	1.5 MPa	0.9 MPa	0.8 MPa	0.4 MPa
E_{OoC}	0.05 MPa	0.0143 MPa	0.0125 MPa	0.01 MPa
ν_{BM}, ν_{OoC}	0.4			
G_{BM} , all directions	E_{BM} , long. and trans./ $2/(1+\nu_{BM})$			
BM damping loss factor	5%			
OoC damping loss factor	10%			

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The magnitude and phase of the traveling wave on the BM are plotted in Figure 2 for BM-only model, baseline model (Fig. 1a), and the three different variations of the OoC (Fig. 1b-d). In contrast to BM-only model, all models with OoC showed more complicated phase roll-off, exhibiting interactions of multiple waves.

FIGURE 2. Magnitude (upper panel) and phase (lower panel) of the traveling wave on BM for (a) BM-only model, (b) baseline model (Fig. 1a), (c) model with larger tunnel (Fig 1b), (d) model with no tunnel (Fig. 1c), (e) model with two tunnels (Fig. 1d). Magnitude was converted in reference to ear canal (EC) pressure using Dong et al. 2013⁵. Dotted line panel (b) indicates where the data was taken to compared with experimental data in Figure 3.

The results in magnitude and phase at $y = 4.6$ mm (dotted line in Fig. 2a) was compared to OCT measurement on mouse post-mortem cochleae⁶ in Figure 3. This location is chosen based on its best frequency in comparison to the experimental data. In addition to the BM-only model, the baseline model and its three variations, we also tested BM-only model with 10 times BM density to see the effect of increasing mass without increasing stiffness. Models with OoC all had a lower magnitude compared to BM-only model. BM-only with 10 times BM density still had a higher magnitude up to best frequency. It also has a faster phase roll-off. The baseline model and the two-tunnel model have a slower phase roll-off due to a plateau of phase roll-off (observed in Fig. 2b and 2e lower panels.)

FIGURE 3. Magnitude (a) and phase (b) of the BM for the baseline model, three variations of the simplified OoC, BM-only model, and the BM-only model with 10x BM density. Experimental data is collected at the apex of intact post-mortem mouse cochleae by Dewey et al. 2021⁶.

Best frequency maps are compared between different variations and the experimental data in Figure 4. Experimental data from Muller et al. 2005⁷ was shifted half and octave down to estimate passive map, and data collected at 80 dB SPL in active cochlea by Nankali et al. 2022⁸ is provided as a reference for the estimation. Surprisingly, we found that adding the OoC on the BM shifted the best frequency at a given location to lower frequencies in the base and middle regions (Fig. 4b), in the same direction of making the cochlear partition softer or adding more mass (Fig. 4c).

Comparisons of results between different models are provided in Table 2.

FIGURE 4. Frequency-location maps. (a) Baseline and two-tunnel, and larger tunnel results. (b) No tunnel, baseline, and BM only results. (c) BM-only results with regular BM density, 3x and 10x BM density.

TABLE 2. Comparison of results from different models.

	Baseline (BL) vs No tunnel (Tnl)	BL vs Larger-Tnl	BL vs Two-Tnls	BL vs BM-only
Phase (Fig. 2&3)	Slower phase roll-off in BL due to sooner phase plateau. It may be a coincident that no-tnl and larger-tnl models have similar results. It seems that more than one waves were in play.		Very similar	One wave
OoC volume ratio	NT/BL = 1.33	BL/LT = 1.42	BL/TT = 1.07	NA
map (Fig. 5)	Surprising to see having one tunnel has made the system stiffer or had the effect of having less mass.	Not much difference but tilted at the apex.	Not much difference, perhaps because the 2nd tunnel is small.	Perhaps can be explained by OoC adding mass to the system, but cannot be completely explained
	The difference between BL and no-tnl cannot be explained by mass difference because the similar OoC mass ratio didn't have such effect between BL and larger-tnl models.			

It has been hypothesized that adding OoC to the BM will not have much effect on the traveling wave on BM, for both that the OoC is extremely soft comparing to the BM, and that it has the same density as the surrounding fluid - i.e. very little stiffness or mass effect was expected. Current findings show the opposite, yet the effect of OoC and fluid tunnels cannot be explained by stiffness or mass alone.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Anes Macic]: This is very interesting work! I appreciate the attention that OoC fluid spaces have recently been getting and I think this insight is very important. I had a very basic question about which two tunnels you were referring to – tunnel of Corti and the outer tunnel, or the cortilymph as a whole and the inner sulcus? Or we ultimately have three tunnels? How should one think about this – what makes a tunnel separate? Do the tunnels change their radius in similar fashion as BM changes its width? I wondered how your Table 1 BM width compares to Richter’s data in different mouse strains (Keiler and Richter 2001), and wondered whether linear interpolation (linear vs linear length) is appropriate? In your results you indicate that adding OoC makes the BF at a given place lower. Is this change consistent with the added mass (from the OoC) (technically making the cochlear partition heavier, not softer)? Finally, I wonder if you could probe local stiffness of your model? How does OoC stiffness compare to BM stiffness in your model? Thank you Yanli!

[Yanli Wang]: Thank you Anes! Current work does not intent to represent any detailed descriptions of the OoC. The tunnels are not specifically tunnel of Corti, outer tunnel, or inner sulcus. It is to probe what would happen to the simplified BM traveling wave in general when attached on top with a body of soft tissue and a fluid tunnel inside. I think the answer is that it is more complicated than we thought. I wish I could have a better answer. The tunnels do change their radius in similar fashion as BM does.

Thanks for bringing up Keiler and Richter 2001! What a wonderful resource. We will look further into it. At a first glance, it seems that the width is 50% - 30% less than reported value. Since the Youngs’ modulus was tuned to match the frequency map, I believe that with a wider BM, we simply will need to retune the Young’s modulus to match the frequency map, and the main finding and message will not be changed by this. We used Burda, Ballast, and Bruns 1988 and Ehret and Frankenreiter 1977 for the geometry of the BM, and Keiler and Richter 2001 is newer and more detailed. We will consult with Keiler and Richter for future work. Thanks for this.

I added some new discussion points in the revision. The shift of adding OoC has similarities to adding mass, but cannot be explained completely by adding mass. Adding mass will result in faster phase roll-off, which is not seen in OoC models (Figure 3).

I will consider probing local stiffness. OoC is 300 times softer than the BM, ranging from 0.05 MPa to 0.0125 MPa from the base to the apex.

Thanks again Anes!

[Anvy Kuriakose]: It would be very informative to discuss what would be the implications of this slower phase roll-off would be and how it would affect the process of hearing!

[Yanli Wang]: The slower phase roll-off could be the result of interactions of different waves in the BM and OoC. It's hard for me to interpret how it would affect the process of hearing, but I can say that simplified BM-only model does not represent the real cochlea well in the aspect that it will have a faster phase roll-off. Thank you!